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Validation and uncertainty study of a comprehensive list of 160 pesticide residues in multi-class vegetables by liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry

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ABSTRACT

A rapid and sensitive liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry method, in electrospray ionization positive mode, has been developed for the determination of 160 selected multi-class pesticides over a 33-min run time. Extracts were obtained using the acetonitrile-based QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe) sample preparation technique. The validation study was carried out on tomato, pear and orange matrices following DG SANCO/2007/3131 of the European Quality Control Guidelines. These matrices represent high water, high sugar and high acidic content commodities, respectively. Matrix influence on recoveries and its effects on ionization were evaluated for the three matrices. Ten out of the 160 pesticides showed very low intensity, linearity and/or sensitivity problems. Linearity was studied in the 5–500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ concentration range. Soft (<20%), medium (20–50%), and strong (>50%) matrix effects were obtained for 69%, 20%, and 11% of the studied compounds, respectively. Recoveries were investigated at the 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ levels, and depending on the commodity, 97%, 98% and 97% of the compounds in tomato, pear and orange, respectively, were in the 70–120% range. More than 90% of the investigated compounds had less or equal to a 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ limit of detection in the studied matrices. The relative standard deviations obtained exceeded 20% in only very few cases. The overall standard deviation obtained in the survey study (0.1551) was used for the method's uncertainty estimation. The expanded uncertainty resulted as being 0.3002 (coverage factor $K = 2$, confidence level 95%). The method was applied on 59 real samples from 14 different kinds of fruits and vegetables. Thirty-three compounds were detected in 50 positive samples.

Keywords: Pesticide residues; Multiresidue method; Mass spectrometry; Validation; Uncertainty

1. Introduction

Pesticides are widely applied on vegetables, fruits and flowers during cultivation and post-harvest storage to ensure quality and to satisfy the requirements of consumers and of the trade. However, these molecules can be very harmful to humans, depending on the levels of pesticides present. Therefore, their maximum concentrations are controlled by the European Union Council Directive 91/414/EEC [1]. Because of strict regulations for low concentration ranges, selective and sensitive methods are needed.

Over recent years, the number of compounds which are only amenable to liquid chromatographic techniques has increased in relation to those amenable to the once widely used gas chromatographic techniques. For this reason, liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC–MS) and tandem mass spectrometry (LC–MS/MS) detection systems are increasingly employed [2–9]. However, the need to determine large numbers of pesticides not amenable to gas chromatography has meant that the high sensitivity, selectivity and quantitation capabilities of the new LC–MS techniques have led to a burgeoning of pesticide multiresidue methods [10]. Several sample preparation procedures are described in the literature. Acetone [10], ethyl-acetate [11–13], methanol [14,15] and acetonitrile-based [16] sample preparation techniques are generally used for multi-class pesticides. These are typically followed by a clean-up step [10,17] in order to eliminate the disruptive effect of the matrix, to concentrate the sample and to enhance sensitivity, etc. In the last few years, the so-called QuEChERS (quick, easy, cheap, effective, rugged and safe) sample preparation procedure has become a widely used technique because of its applicability on a wide range of pesticides [2,16,18].

Besides some single residue methods, with which either a single compound, or a group of specific compounds, can be measured [4,7], there are several multiresidue methods designed for the determination of more than 20 [12,13,15] pesticides. Their retention time, along with two specific transitions and their intensity ratio, are usually enough to identify the compound when using low-resolution LC–MS/MS instruments. As this technique is usually combined with electrospray ionization (ESI), the interference between a molecule and some components of the matrix, especially at the beginning of the chromatogram, can produce ionization problems [19]. The signal intensity of the measurable pesticide is considerably dependent on the matrix. These problems become highly significant when the measured

concentration of the pesticide exceeds the maximum residue level. Therefore the aim is to solve these problems so as to avoid false positive or false negative findings at the maximum residue limit (MRL) value.

In this paper, a sensitive multiresidue pesticide method was developed for the determination of 160 multi-class pesticides, using an LC-MS/MS system with an electrospray interface, operated in positive ionization mode. These compounds were selected because of their relevance in routine monitoring studies. The method was applied on one vegetable matrix – tomato – and two fruit matrices – pear and orange – which together represent high water, high sugar and high acidic content commodities, respectively. The validation and uncertainty studies applied give clear evidence of the robustness and quality of the proposed multiresidue method [20]. Furthermore, the method was applied to real samples with good results.

2. Experimental

2.1. Reagents and materials

Ultra gradient HPLC-grade acetonitrile was purchased from J.T. Baker (Deventer, The Netherlands). Deionized water was obtained from a Milli-Q SP Reagent Water System (Millipore; Bedford, MA, USA). Formic acid (98% purity) and anhydrous magnesium sulphate were ordered from Fluka-Sigma-Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Each sample was filtered through a 13 mm × 0.45 µm PTFE filter before injection, whilst PSA-bonded (primary secondary amine) silica was used as a sample clean-up step—both of them were from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). Acetic acid (Merck; Darmstadt, Germany) and sodium acetate-3-hydrate (Panreac; Castellon de Valles, Barcelona, Spain) were used for the sample preparation procedure. Analytical-grade standards were obtained from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) and Riedel-de Haen (Selze, Germany) and were stored at –30 °C. Standard stock solutions were prepared by dissolving the crystalline standards in acetonitrile at a concentration range between 1000 and 5000 µg ml⁻¹. Individual standard solutions for the optimization and two standard mix solutions for the calibration were prepared from the stock standards and they were kept in the fridge at –18 °C before use.

2.2. Sample treatment

The well-known and accepted QuEChERS sample preparation procedure was applied to all the samples. After homogenization with the stainless-steel cutter (Sammic, Azpeitia, Spain), a 15 g portion of homogenized sample was weighed in a 50-ml PTFE centrifuge tube. A 200 μl volume of 25 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ triphenyl phosphate (TPP) standard in acetonitrile (surrogate standard) was added as a quality control during the entire procedure. Then, 15 ml of acetonitrile were added with 6 g MgSO_4 and 2.5 g sodium acetate-3-hydrate and the samples were shaken vigorously by hand for min. The extract was then centrifuged (3700 rpm) for 5 min. A ml volume of the supernatant was removed to a 1-ml PTFE centrifuge tube containing 750 mg of MgSO_4 and 250 mg of PSA. The extract was shaken in a vortex intensively for 20 s and centrifuged again (3700 rpm) for 5 min. Following this, an aliquot of the supernatant was evaporated under a nitrogen stream and reconstituted with acetonitrile/water (20/80) for LC analysis. Prior to injection into the LC-MS system, the sample was filtered through a 0.45- μm PTFE filter. With this treatment, a 1 ml sample extract represents 1 g of sample.

For the matrix-matched standard calibration, “blank” extracts were used. Fruit and vegetable samples were purchased from an organic market and the preparation procedure was the same as that mentioned above.

2.3. LC-MS analysis

For the LC analysis, an Agilent 1200 HPLC system with a binary pump was used. This was equipped with a reversed-phase C8 analytical column of 150 mm \times 4.6 mm and 5 μm particle size (Agilent Zorbax Eclipse XDB). The mobile phases, A and B, were Milli-Q water with 0.1% formic acid and acetonitrile, respectively. The gradient program started with 20% of B, constant for 3 min, followed by a linear gradient up to 100% B in 30 min, then constant for 3 min. After this 33-min run time, 12 min of post-time followed using the initial 20% of B. The flow rate was constant, 0.6 ml min^{-1} during the whole process and 10 μl of sample was injected in every case.

For the mass spectrometric analysis, an Agilent 6410 Triple-Quad LC/MS system was applied. The ESI source was operated in positive ionization mode and its parameters were as follows: gas temperature, 325 $^{\circ}\text{C}$; gas flow, 12 l min^{-1} ; nebulizer gas, 50 psi; capillary voltage, 5000 V. Nitrogen was served as the nebulizer and collision gas. Five time windows with a ± 1 min overlapping range around the

borders were constructed. The start time of the first, second, third, fourth and fifth segments were 0, 14.1, 18.1, 20.9 and 23.4 min, respectively. Fig. 1 shows the total ion chromatogram of 160 pesticides (all of them at 100 ng ml^{-1} concentrations). Agilent Mass Hunter Data Acquisition; Qualitative Analysis and Quantitative Analysis software was used for method development and data acquisition.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Target multiresidue scope selection

A comprehensive list of pesticides, encompassing four groups, was considered as the scope. They were as follows:

Group 1. Forty LC-amenable pesticides were chosen (Table 1) from Annex I of the European Union Directive (91/414/EEC). They represent 23% of the current Annex I list.

Group 2. Twenty-one pesticides with important health implications were selected. These are not authorized in the European Union but are manufactured or allowed in third countries.

Group 3. All the LC-amenable pesticides from the list of the current European Union Proficiency Test (EUPT) for Fruits and Vegetables were selected (www.crl-pesticides.eu) [21].

Group 4. Fifty-six compounds, which give positive findings, were collected from the www.pesticides-online.com database over the period 2000–2007 [22].

Taking these four groups into account, the total scope of the developed LC method comprises 160 pesticides.

3.2. MS parameters

The MS parameters were optimized with the objectives of: (i) obtaining the protonated molecule and (ii) selecting those transitions with higher molecular mass in order to avoid the disruptive effects of the matrix, as far as possible.

The optimization of the precursor ion and product ions was carried out by the injection of $1 \mu\text{l}$ of the individual pesticide standard solution ($1\text{--}3 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ in acetonitrile) directly into the mass

spectrometer into a constant flow of acetonitrile/water (50/50) with a flow rate of 0.2 ml min^{-1} . Different fragmentor voltages (60, 90, 120 and 150 V) were applied and once the optimal fragmentor voltage was found, different collision energies (5, 10, 15 and 20 V) were investigated. Where possible, the two most intense transitions were chosen for merging and creating the method. The most intense transition was used as a quantifier whilst the other was used as a qualifier peak for the confirmatory analysis. These optimization parameters are included in [Table 1](#). In some cases, only two transitions were obtained and therefore no selection was possible. For spinosyn D, there was only one transition, over all of the conditions studied, thus making it impossible to obtain an adequate identification. Obtaining low masses also represented a disadvantage given the consequent decrease in specificity. Demeton-S-methyl (m/z 89.2 and 61) and cyprodinil (m/z 92.9 and 76.9) yielded low mass ions, as did cyromazine and thiocyclam; which, additionally, are eluted very close to the front of the chromatogram alongside the matrix components. For this reason, higher background noise was observed ([Table 1](#)).

In the case of phosmet, the fragmentation was only possible at extreme conditions and it was impossible to get more than one product ion. For these reasons, both the protonated molecule and sodium ion adduct were used as precursor ions.

3.3. Compound identification

The identification procedure for pesticide residues in food commodities was based on the following factors: the use of the retention time, two transitions and the selected reaction monitoring (SRM) ratio of the transitions. Peak shapes were adequate in most cases, except for some particular pesticides. In these cases, peak broadening or multiple peaks occurred, such as with dimethomorph and XMC. Isomers of these pesticides are shown in [Fig. 2](#).

In wide-scope multiresidue methods like the one presented here, some related difficulties may occur due to the presence of isomers, identical precursor ions, or common transitions, etc... One such problem appeared with the emamectin benzoate standard, which contains a mixture of both isomers—around 80% emamectin B1A and about 20% emamectin B1B. The optimization for this compound was done for the mixture as a whole, not for each separate isomer. In the analysis of this compound in the sample, two peaks with very different

abundance were present. The first one (retention time 18.5 min) presented a higher intensity than the second one (retention time 19.2 min). But as the optimization was done for the mixture as a whole, their ionization was not fully optimized, so it cannot be said that the reason for the different intensities is as a result of the ratio of the compounds in the mixture. This fact can produce difficulties in their correct quantitation. Another example is the spinosad standard, which is a mixture of spinosyn A and spinosyn D (50:50). Their precursor ions have different masses and retention times, however. Consequently, they do not cause difficulties regarding identification.

Three pairs of pesticides presented common transitions: therbuthylazine–propazine; prometryn–terbutryn and diuron–fluometuron (see Fig. 3). The first two pairs have only one transition in common, and although it is possible to identify therbuthylazine and propazine by using the retention times, it is not possible in the case prometryn–terbutryn because their retention times differ by only 0.1 min (Table 1). What's more, their SRM ratios are very similar. Therefore, it is not possible to differentiate between them with the developed method. This is similarly the case with diuron–fluometuron; although these compounds have different retention times, thus allowing them to be identified in this way (Table 1).

3.4. Comparison of SRM ratios

The values of the SRM ratios for all of the two transitions selected are between 5% and 100%; only 5% of the compounds presented a SRM ratio lower than 7%, allowing a correct identification and quantification in the concentration range studied. More than 90% of the compounds presented SRM variability lower than 25% in this concentration range. This is in accordance with the DG SANCO European Quality Control guidelines, based on ion-ratio statistics for the transitions monitored. Ten percent of the pesticides presented higher variability values (25–80%). This is as a consequence of important deviations, mainly at low concentration levels (bendiocarb, carbofuran, ethion), or very low responses (<7%) of the quantifier ion (metobromuron). Furthermore, this can be affected by the matrix (butocarboxin in tomato, difenoconazole in pear, etc.). Only in three cases are SRM ratios higher than 50%: fipronil in tomato, and triadimenol and alachlor in pear.

For phosmet, spinosin D and methomyl, the calculation of the SRM ratios was not possible because the intensity of the qualifier transition was very low.

3.5. Validation study: linearity and matrix effects

The seven-point-calibration curves in solvent and in the three matrices (tomato, pear and orange) were constructed and compared at the 5–10–25–50–100–250 and 500 ng ml⁻¹ concentration levels. This comparison gave information not only about linearity and sensitivity but also about matrix effects (signal suppression or enhancement). The results of the present study showed that 82% of the pesticides presented correlation coefficients (R^2) higher than 0.99, and 96% of the compounds were higher than 0.96 in all calibration curves. These results are included in [Table 2](#). In most cases, bad linearity in the range studied ($R^2 < 0.9$) was due to low sensitivity, especially in the tomato and pear matrices. This occurred with acephate, isocarbofos, lufenuron, propargite and pyridaben ([Table 2](#)). Ten pesticides (alanycarb, chlorpropham, cymoxanil, diafenthiuron, dichlofluanid, dinotefuran, phosmet, prophaphos, pyrimidifen and spiromesifen) were deleted from the list of pesticides studied because of this low sensitivity; meaning it was not possible to get reliable information for further studies. Therefore, the following assays were carried out with just the 150 remaining compounds.

The study of the ratio of the slopes, in solvent and in matrix, provided information about the matrix effects. Depending on the decrease/increase in the percentage of the slope, different matrix effect could be observed: it was considered to be a mild signal suppression or enhancement effect between -20% and 0% and between 0% and +20%; it was considered to be of medium effect when the slope values were between -50% and -20% or +20% and +50%; and it was considered to be a strong effect of signal suppression or enhancement below -50% or above +50%. These distributions depended not only on the matrix effect but also on the combination of the compound-matrix ([Fig. 4](#)). In the tomato matrix, more than 75% of the compounds presented very low signal suppression (-20% to +20%). The pear and orange matrices had similar values with a slightly lower percentage. It is noticeable that in some cases, strong suppression appeared in all three matrices, but in pear and orange, this effect was significantly higher—in comparison to that in tomato. Strong signal enhancement was not very important in any of the matrices or compounds. To sum up, soft, medium and strong signal suppression or enhancement was obtained in 69%, 20% and 11% of the compounds, respectively—when averaging the values of the three matrices.

3.6. Recovery study

For the recovery study, spiked samples were prepared from each of the three matrices and examined at 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ spiking levels. The QuEChERS method was carried out five times at each spiking level and on each matrix. The data evaluation was carried out by comparing the peak intensities of the spiked samples to those obtained by matrix-matched standard calibration. Extracted “blank” matrices may have contained some of the investigated pesticides. Therefore, blank-correction from the calibration samples and also from the spiked samples was necessary during the analysis. The distribution of the recoveries is shown in Fig. 5. More than 95% of the pesticides under study presented recoveries between 80% and 110% representing 85%, 65% and 78% for tomato, pear and orange, respectively. These recoveries were in the acceptance range of the DG SANCO/2007/3131 of the European Quality Control Guidelines: 70–120% in all cases, except for cyromazine and fluazifop, which showed recoveries lower than 70% in every matrix. In the case of fipronil, its recoveries were low, less than 70% in the orange and tomato matrices, with extremely high standard deviations and relative standard deviation. The reason for this is probably low sensitivity (see Table 2) of the pesticide (limits of detection (LOD) 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ in the orange and tomato matrices).

Some pesticides showed a clear trend towards low recoveries in the three matrices studied, for example: fluroxypyr (78%, 76%, 80%) and thiophanate ethyl (84%, 84%, 78%) in tomato, pear and orange, respectively. In other cases, low recoveries were only detected in specific compound/matrix combinations, such as teflubenzuron (75%) in pear. The generally good recoveries obtained support the adequacy of the method and its application over a wide multiresidue range.

3.7. Limits of detection

LODs were evaluated by injecting standard solutions into blank-matrix at the 0.1–0.25–0.5 and 1 ng ml^{-1} concentration levels. The LOD was settled as the value where the intensities for both transitions were significantly higher than the background, and where the signal-to-noise ratio was higher than 3. More than 90% of the cases were below or equal to 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ and the most frequent LOD was 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (see Fig. 6). These comply with the MRLs established by EU legislation. For

most of the pesticides, the detection limits were not affected, or were only slightly affected, by the studied matrices. The exceptions were: teflubenzuron (1, 5, 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and procymidone (5, 0.1, 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ LODs) for tomato, pear and orange, respectively. Other compounds resulted as being extremely sensitive; for example: diazinon or pirimiphos-methyl (0.1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ LOD in each matrix). In some cases, there are compounds in which the matrix is very relevant to the LODs; for example, clofentezine in orange and fipronil in pear (25 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ LODs). Spinosyn D and methomyl only presented one transition (methomyl has, in fact, got two, but only one showed good sensitivity). Therefore, they are not suitable for the limits of detection criteria established (the lowest concentration where both transitions appear).

3.8. Repeatability

The repeatability study was carried out with 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ matrix-matched standard calibration points, injected five times, to evaluate the RSDs of the signal intensities. Repeatability was below 20%, except for: difenoconazole in all three matrices, propamocarb in tomato and pear and propargite in the tomato matrix. This complies with the RSD accepted by the DG SANCO/2007/3131 of the European Quality Control Guidelines [23]. At the 10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ concentration level, the RSDs for 15 compounds (aclonifen, bendiocarb, carbaryl, clofentezine, cyromazine, dicloran, fipronil, fluroxypyr, hexaflumuron, indoxacarb, metobromuron, monolinuron, thiabendazole, thiamethoxam and XMC) were generally higher than 20%—between 20% and 50%.

3.9. Estimation of measurement uncertainty (MU)

The estimation of the MU has been carried out following an empirical model (“top-down”); by using the data derived from the validation of the method. This includes the sample preparation, standards dilution, and chromatographic and MS detection variabilities, measured as RSD.

The recovery was studied on 150 compounds at 10 and 100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ levels in three matrices for five replicates. Every pesticide has its own variability in each matrix and at each level (RSD). The estimation of the MU of the method was evaluated on the basis of the 150 pesticides, which are included within six groups

of data: three groups according to the matrix (tomato, pear and orange), two groups according to the concentration level (10 and 100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and one overall group (all three matrices at both levels). The mean recoveries, the standard deviations and the RSDs of these six groups are included in Table 3. The matrices studied show small differences regardless of the mean recovery (93.8, 87.5, 89.4) with practically the same RSDs throughout. As was expected, the lower fortification level (10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) gave lower recovery and higher RSDs than the higher level (100 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), as is represented in Table 3. The overall mean recovery (90.2%) and its RSD (15.5%) show the adequacy of the whole method. With the overall RSD (0.1501) resulting from this intra-laboratory study (Table 3), and considering a coverage factor ($k = 2$)—an expanded uncertainty was estimated as being 0.3002 [20,24].

This expanded uncertainty value is in agreement with the estimation made from the European Proficiency Test schemes, where a generalized MU budget of $\pm 50\%$ is applicable as the default value. That value is included in the DG SANCO/2007/3131 of the European Quality Control Guidelines [24].

3.10. Application to real samples

Real samples were taken as part of the Andalucía Pesticide Monitoring Program. Fifty-nine samples of cucumber, pear, apple, strawberry mandarin, red pepper, tomato, eggplant, banana, nectarine, melon, watermelon, lemon and kiwi were chosen as representative of different groups of fruit and vegetables. Different matrix-matched calibrations were settled upon, depending on the characteristics of the matrix. Three calibration curves were measured (tomato, pear and orange), which represented commodities with high water, high sugar and high acidic content and each of them was comprised of five calibration points at the 5, 10, 50, 100 and 500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ levels. As the matrices used for the calibration were classified into three groups, the samples had to be classified in the same way. Analogously, cucumber, red pepper, tomato and eggplant samples are in the “tomato group”; banana, apple, strawberry, pear, nectarine, melon, watermelon and kiwi are in the “pear group”; whereas, mandarin and lemon are in the “orange group.” Every sample, except banana, could be classified into one of the three groups. For this reason, banana has to be considered as a discrete matrix. Banana is similar to pear because of its high sugar content, but differs from the other matrices because of its high lipid and fat content. Nevertheless, although pear is not the best choice for comparison with banana, these samples were analyzed using the pear matrix-

matched calibration.

From the 150 pesticides present in 59 samples—33 compounds were found in 50 positive samples. The concentrations found were lower than $100 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$, except for imazalil ($1278 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) and malathion ($1021 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) in the mandarin sample. However, they did not exceed their MRLs (5 and 7 mg kg^{-1} , respectively) [24]. The reason for their appearance was probably because these chemicals are used particularly for the post-harvest storage of citrus fruits. None of the prohibited pesticides in the European Union gave positive findings in these samples.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the determination of 160 multi-class pesticides was evaluated using liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry. The linearity, matrix effect, recovery, limits of detection and reproducibility were studied in tomato, pear and orange matrices. Ten pesticides showed sensitivity and/or linearity problems within the investigated calibration range ($5\text{--}500 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$).

Soft (<20%), medium (20–50%) and strong (>50%) matrix effects were obtained in 67%, 21% and 12% of the compounds, respectively. Out of the non-sensitive compounds (alanycarb, chlorpropham, cymoxanil, diafenthiuron, dichlofluanid, dinotefuran, phosmet, prophaphos, pyrimidifen and spiromesifen), the recoveries (at $100 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) were in the accepted range: 97%, 98% and 97% in tomato, pear and orange, respectively; except for three pesticides (cyromazine, fipronil and fluazifop)—the recoveries of which were below 70%. The RSDs exceeded the 20% level in only a few cases, mainly in the tomato matrix. The method has been applied to 59 real samples of different kinds of fruit and vegetables. Thirty-three compounds were found in 50 positive samples. None of the pesticides prohibited in Europe (Group 2) reported positive findings and only imazalil and malathion exceeded the 1 mg kg^{-1} concentration in a mandarin sample. In any case, the concentrations found were below their EU MRLs.

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Fig. 1. Total ion chromatogram of 160 multi-class pesticides at the 100 ng ml⁻¹ concentration level and the five time windows.

Fig. 2. Example for isomers.

Fig. 3. Example for common transitions.

Fig. 4. Distribution of matrix effects.

Fig. 5. Data distribution of recoveries.

Fig. 6. Distribution of the limits of detection.

Table 1. Detection and chromatographic parameters for the selected compounds (Group 1: included in Annex I; Group 2: non-authorized pesticides in the EU; Group 3: LC-amenable compounds of the European Proficiency Test; Group 4: positive findings in the EU from 2000 to 2007).

Pesticide	Group	t _R (min)	Peak width (min)	Quantitation MRM1	Confirmation MRM2	Fragmentor (V)	Collision energy 1 (V)	Collision energy 2 (V)
Acephate	3, 4	3.2	0.62	184.1/143.0	184.1/125.0	90	5	15
Acetamiprid	1, 3	11.3	0.36	223.0/126.0	223.0/56.0	120	20	15
Aclonifen	4	23.5	0.38	265.1/248.1	365.1/218.1	120	15	20
Alachlor	4	23.2	0.60	270.0/162.0	270.0/238.0	90	15	15
Alanycarb	2	22.8	0.35	400.1/238.1	400.1/150.2	90	5	20
Albendazole	4	13.6	0.41	266.0/234.0	266.0/192.0	120	20	20
Aldicarb	3	13.9	0.36	213.0/89.0	213.0/116.0	120	15	10
Aldicarb sulfone	3	5.3	0.37	223.0/86.0	223.0/148.0	120	10	5
Aldicarb sulfoxide	3	3.4	0.29	207.0/89.0	207.0/132.0	60	10	5
Anilofos	2	24.7	0.43	368.0/199.0	368.0/171.0	120	10	20
Atrazine	4	17.3	0.59	216.0/174.0	216.0/146.0	120	15	20
Azinphos-ethyl	4	23.1	0.41	368.1/132.2	368.1/160.2	150	15	10
Azoxystrobin	1, 3	21.1	0.41	404.0/372.0	404.0/344.0	120	10	20
Benalaxyl	1	24.1	0.54	326.0/294.0	326.0/208.0	120	5	15
Bendiocarb	4	16.6	0.34	224.0/109.0	224.0/167.0	90	15	5
Bromacil	4	14.2	0.36	261.0/205.0	261.0/188.0	90	10	20
Bromuconazole	4	20.5 and 21.58	0.52	378.0/159.0	378.0/70.0	120	20	20
Bupirimate	3	19.9	0.49	317.0/166.0	317.0/108.0	150	20	20
Buprofezin	3	24.9	0.54	306.0/201.0	306.0/116.0	120	10	15
Butocarboxin	4	13.0	0.41	213.0/75.0	213.0/156.0	120	15	5
Butoxycarboxin	4	4.8	0.41	223.0/106.0	223.0/166.0	90	5	5
Cambendazole	4	9.1	0.99	303.0/261.0	303.0/217.0	120	15	20
Carbaryl	3	17.2	0.39	202.0/145.0	202.0/127.0	140	10	20
Carbendazim	1, 3	3.4	0.29	192.0/160.0	192.0/132.0	150	15	20
Carbofuran	3	16.6	0.52	222.0/123.0	222.0/165.0	90	20	10
Chlorbromuron	4	21.0	0.30	293.0/182.0	293.0/204.0	120	15	20
Chlorfenvinphos	3	23.7 and 24.5	0.42	359.0/155.1	359.0/126.9	120	10	15
Chloridazon	1	10.0	0.48	222.0/104.0	222.0/92.0	120	20	20
Chlorotoluron	1	16.6	0.39	213.0/72.0	213.0/140.0	120	20	20
Chloroxuron	4	20.4	0.31	291.0/72.0	291.0/218.0	120	20	20
Chlorpropham	1, 3, 4	3.3	0.40	214.0/171.8	214.0/153.9	90	5	15
Chromafenozide	2	22.7	0.46	395.2/175.1	395.2/339.2	90	10	5
Cymoxanil	4	3.9	0.39	199.0/128.0	199.0/171.0	90	15	10
Cyproconazole	4	20.1	0.56	292.0/70.0	292.0/125.0	120	20	20
Cyprodinil	1, 3, 4	18.8	0.48	226.2/92.9	226.2/76.9	150	40	40
Cyromazine	4	2.3	0.26	167.0/85.0	167.0/125.0	120	20	15
Deet	2	17.6	0.91	192.1/119.0	192.1/91.1	120	15	20
Demeton-S-methyl	4	15.3	0.51	231.0/89.2	231.0/61.0	80	10	20
Desethylterbutylazine	4	15.2	0.70	202.0/146.0	202.0/110.0	120	15	20
Diafenthiuron	2	29.7	0.43	385.2/329.2	385.2/287.1	120	20	20
Diazinon	3	25.3	0.71	305.0/169.0	305.0/153.0	120	15	20
Dichlorvos	3, 4	15.5	0.36	221.1/109.0	221.1/144.9	150	15	10
Dicloran	4	19.6	0.30	207.0/190.1	207.0/160.1	150	15	20
Diethofencarb	4	20.6	0.41	268.2/226.2	268.2/180.2	90	5	15
Difenoconazole	4	23.59 double peak	0.95	406.0/251.0	406.0/337.0	120	20	15
Difenoxyuron	4	17.6	0.39	287.0/72.0	287.0/123.0	90	20	20
Diflubenzuron	4	22.2	0.35	311.0/158.0	311.0/141.0	120	10	20
Dimethoate	1, 3	11.2	0.48	230.0/199.0	230.0/171.0	90	5	10
Dimethomorph	1, 3	18.8 and 19.1	0.84	388.0/301.0	388.0/165.0	150	20	20
Dimethylvinphos	2	21.1	0.36	330.9/205.0	330.9/127.1	90	20	10
Dinotefuran	2	3.8	0.36	203.1/129.1	203.1/157.1	90	5	5
Diuron	4	17.7	0.44	233.0/72.0	233.0/160.0	120	20	20
Edifenphos	2	23.3	0.38	311.0/173.0	311.0/283.1	120	5	10
Emamectin benzoate	2, 4	18.5 and 19.2	0.27	886.5/158.2	886.5/302.4	90	20	20
Ethiofencarb	4	17.8	0.60	226.0/107.0	226.0/164.0	60	15	5
Ethion	4	28.6	0.48	385.1/199.0	385.1/171.0	90	5	10
Ethiprole	2	20.1	0.54	396.9/351.0	396.9/255.1	120	15	20
Ethoxyquin	4	15.7	0.30	218.0/190.0	218.0/202.0	150	20	20
Fenamiphos	1	20.8	0.65	304.0/217.0	304.0/234.0	120	20	15
Fenarimol	1, 3, 4	20.5	0.41	331.1/268.2	331.1/259.1	150	20	20
Fenazaquin	4	27.8	0.48	307.3/161.3	307.3/147.2	150	15	15
Fenbendazole	4	16.5	0.44	300.0/268.0	300.0/159.0	120	20	20
Fenhexamid	1, 3	21.3	0.44	302.0/97.0	302.0/55.0	90	25	30
Fenobucarb	2	20.6	0.45	208.1/95.0	208.1/152.1	90	10	5
Fenoxycarb	4	22.6	0.38	302.2/88.2	302.2/116.2	90	20	5
Fenuron	4	10.0	0.63	165.0/72.0	165.0/120.0	90	20	15
Fipronil	1, 4	24.3	0.26	437.3/368.2	437.3/315.3	150	15	20

Flazasulfuron	1	19.0	0.46	408.0/182.0	408.0/301.0	120	20	10
Fluacrypyrim	2	26.6	0.51	427.1/145.1	427.1/205.1	90	20	5
Fluazifop	4	20.3	0.41	328.2/282.2	382.2/254.2	150	15	20
Flufenoxuron	4	27.5	0.45	489.0/158.0	489.0/306.0	120	15	15
Fluometuron	4	17.3	0.44	233.0/72.0	233.0/160.0	120	20	20
Fluquinconazole	4	21.5	0.41	376.1/307.1	376.1/349.2	150	20	20
Fluroxypyr	1	14.5	0.33	255.0/181.0	255.0/209.0	120	20	15
Hexaflumuron	4	25.1	0.43	461.0/158.0	461.0/141.0	120	15	15
Hexythiazox	3	28.3	0.40	353.1/168.2	353.1/228.2	120	20	10
Imazalil	1, 3	13.9	0.34	297.0/159.0	297.0/255.0	150	20	15
Imidacloprid	3	10.3	0.41	256.0/175.0	256.0/209.0	90	15	15
Indoxacarb	1, 3, 4	26.2	0.34	528.1/249.1	528.1/150.2	150	15	15
Iprodione	1, 3	22.7	0.42	330.0/245.0	330.0/101.0	90	15	20
Isocarbofos	2	20.3	0.38	312.0/270.0	312.0/236.0	90	15	15
Isofenfos methyl	2, 3	25.4	0.42	231.0/121.0	231.0/199.0	90	15	15
Isoprocarb	2	18.7	0.57	194.1/95.1	194.1/152.0	90	15	5
Isoproturon	1	17.6	0.44	207.0/72.0	207.0/165.0	120	20	10
Kresoxim-methyl	1, 3, 4	24.2	0.40	336.2/246.2	336.2/229.2	150	15	20
Lenacil	4	15.1	0.54	235.0/153.0	235.0/136.0	90	10	20
Linuron	1, 3	20.6	0.43	249.0/160.0	249.0/182.0	90	20	15
Lufenuron	4	26.8	0.31	511.0/158.0	511.0/141.0	120	20	20
Malathion	3	23.0	0.55	331.0/99.0	331.0/127.0	90	20	10
Mebendazole	4	13.7	0.36	296.0/264.0	296.0/105.0	120	20	20
Metalaxyl	3	17.5	0.57	280.0/220.0	280.0/160.0	120	10	20
Metamitron	4	9.2	0.41	203.0/175.0	203.0/104.0	120	15	20
Methamidophos	1, 3, 4	3.2	0.41	142.1/94.1	142.1/125.0	90	10	10
Methidathion	3	20.7	0.43	303.0/85.0	303.0/145.0	60	15	5
Methiocarb	1, 3	20.3	0.54	226.0/169.0	226.0/121.0	90	5	20
Methiocarb sulfoxide	3	8.1	0.21	242.0/185.0	242.0/170.0	90	10	20
Methomyl	3	6.2	0.43	185.0/128.0	185.0/99.0	90	5	10
Methoxyfenozide	1, 4	22.3	0.35	369.3/149.2	369.3/133.1	90	15	20
Metobromuron	4	18.6	0.35	260.0/149.0	260.0/171.0	120	10	20
Metolachlor	4	23.0	0.60	284.0/252.0	284.0/176.0	120	10	20
Metolcarb	4	15.2	0.54	166.0/109.0	166.0/91.0	60	5	20
Miconazole	4	17.7	0.42	417.0/159.0	417.0/227.0	120	20	20
Monocrotophos	3	4.8	0.67	224.0/127.0	224.0/98.0	60	10	15
Monolinuron	4	17.9	0.47	215.0/126.0	215.0/148.0	120	15	15
Monuron	4	14.6	0.36	199.0/72.0	199.0/126.0	120	15	20
Myclobutanil	3, 4	21.2	0.60	289.2/70.2	289.2/125.1	150	15	20
Neburon	4	23.3	0.49	275.0/88.0	275.0/114.0	120	15	10
Nitempyram	2	4.6	0.29	271.0/225.0	271.0/99.0	90	10	10
Omethoate	4	3.3	0.22	214.1/183.0	214.1/125.0	90	5	20
Oxadixyl	4	14.5	1.00	279.0/219.0	279.0/133.0	90	5	20
Oxamyl	1, 3	5.1	0.51	237.0/72.0	237.0/90.0	60	10	5
Oxfendazole	4	10.3	0.41	316.0/191.0	316.0/284.0	120	20	15
Parathion-methyl	3, 4	24.7	0.45	292.0/236.0	292.0/264.0	90	10	5
Penconazole	3	22.4	0.40	284.0/70.0	284.0/159.0	90	15	20
Phosmet	1, 3, 4	21.1	0.37	318.1/160.2	339.0/253.7	90	10	5
Pirimicarb	1, 3, 4	6.6	0.58	239.2/72.2	239.2/182.1	150	20	15
Pirimiphos-methyl	1, 3, 4	25.3	0.50	306.2/164.2	306.2/108.2	150	20	20
Prochloraz	3	19.5	0.38	376.0/308.0	376.0/266.0	90	10	15
Procymidone	1, 3, 4	23.0	0.41	284.3/95.0	284.3/256.3	150	20	15
Promecarb	4	21.1	0.60	208.0/109.0	208.0/151.0	60	15	5
Prometryn	4	16.4	0.60	242.0/200.0	242.0/158.0	90	20	20
Propamocarb	1, 4	3.2	0.31	189.2/102.1	189.2/144.1	150	15	10
Propaphos	2	23.0	0.45	305.1/221.1	305.1/263.2	90	10	5
Propargite	3, 4	29.0	0.43	373.2/81.0	373.2/175.0	150	30	20
Propazine	4	19.8	0.60	230.0/146.0	230.0/188.0	120	20	20
Pyridaben	4	29.6	0.45	365.2/147.3	365.2/309.2	120	20	10
Pyridaphenthion	4	21.7	0.46	341.1/189.2	341.1/205.1	120	20	20
Pyrimethanil	1, 3	15.6	0.73	200.0/107.0	200.0/183.0	120	20	20
Pyrimidifen	2	20.7	0.46	378.1/184.1	378.1/150.2	120	20	20
Pyriproxyfen	3	27.4	0.42	322.0/96.0	322.0/185.0	120	10	20
Quinalphos	4	24.1	0.48	299.1/147.2	299.1/163.2	150	20	20
Quinoxifen	1, 3	25.9	0.51	308.1/196.9	308.1/271.9	150	35	25
Simazine	4	14.5	0.38	202.0/132.0	202.0/124.0	120	20	20
Spinosyn A	1, 3	17.5	0.39	732.5/142.0	732.5/98.0	150	20	20
Spinosyn D	1, 3	18.3	0.44	746.5/142.0	No second trans.	120	20	No second trans.
Spiromesifen	4	30.4	0.81	371.0/273.0	371.0/255.0	60	5	20
Spiroxamine	1, 3	16.2	0.52	298.0/144.0	298.0/100.0	120	20	20
Tebuconazole	3	21.7	0.46	308.0/70.0	308.0/125.0	90	20	20
Tebufenozide	4	23.7	0.42	353.2/133.1	353.2/296.9	150	15	5
Tebufenpyrad	4	26.3	0.45	334.1/145.1	334.1/171.1	150	20	20
Teflubenzuron	4	25.4	0.40	381.0/158.0	381.0/141.0	90	20	20
Terbutylazine	4	20.3	0.60	230.0/174.0	230.0/146.0	120	15	20
Terbutrin	4	16.5	0.63	242.0/186.0	242.0/158.0	120 (90)	20	20
Thiabendazole	1, 3	3.6	0.22	202.0/175.0	202.0/131.0	90	5	10
Thiacloprid	1	13.3	0.36	253.0/126.0	253.0/186.0	120	20	10
Thiametoxam	1	7.5	0.51	292.0/211.0	292.0/181.0	90	10	20

Thiocyclam	2	2.9	0.24	182.0/137.0	182.0/73.0	90	15	20
Thiophanate-ethyl	4	18.9	0.41	371.1/151.1	371.1/325.1	90	20	10
Tolfenpyrad	2	26.1	0.48	384.1/197.1	384.1/171.1	120	20	20
TPP	Surrogate d std.	24.6	0.37	327.0/77.2	327.0/152.2	120	35	30
Triadimefon	3, 4	21.6	0.49	294.2/197.1	294.2/225.0	150	10	10
Triadimenol	3, 4	19.5 and 19.9	0.45	296.2/70.2	296.2/227.0	60	10	5
Triazophos	3	22.8	0.41	314.1/162.2	314.1/286.2	150	20	10
Triclocarban	4	24.8	0.48	315.0/128.0	315.0/162.0	120	15	20
Trifloxystrobin	1, 3, 4	26.4	0.43	409.2/186.2	409.2/206.2	120	20	10
Triflumizol	4	22.9	0.54	346.0/278.0	346.0/73.0	90	5	10
Triflumuron	4	24.1	0.37	359.0/156.0	359.0/139.0	120	15	20
XMC	2	16.4 and 16.9 and 17.5	1.12	180.1/123.0	180.1/95.1	60	5	20

Table 2. Linearity and matrix effects.

Pesticide	Solvent		Tomato matrix		Pear matrix		Orange matrix		Slope matrix/slope solvent			Matrix effect (%) = $(1 - (\text{slope matrix/slope solvent})) \times 100$		
	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Slope	R ²	Tomato	Pear	Orange	Tomato	Pear	Orange
Acephate	79.6	0.983	37.1	0.890	92.7	0.981	67.5	0.992	0.466	1.164	0.848	-53.4	16.4	-15.2
Acetamiprid	144.2	0.998	126.1	0.998	140.0	0.998	153.1	1.000	0.875	0.971	1.062	-12.5	-2.9	6.2
Aclonifen	40.0	0.999	33.3	1.000	23.0	0.987	26.0	0.994	0.831	0.575	0.649	-16.9	-42.5	-35.1
Alachlor	46.6	0.997	46.0	1.000	40.9	0.999	39.1	0.995	0.988	0.877	0.840	-1.2	-12.3	-16.0
Albendazole	748.7	0.998	645.2	0.999	677.9	0.998	721.6	0.992	0.862	0.905	0.964	-13.8	-9.5	-3.6
Aldicarb	34.0	0.975	25.0	0.986	31.3	0.995	30.5	0.990	0.734	0.920	0.895	-26.6	-8.0	-10.5
Aldicarb sulfone	23.9	0.988	23.8	0.988	25.8	0.972	31.4	0.985	0.998	1.083	1.317	-0.2	8.3	31.7
Aldicarb sulfoxide	32.8	0.997	29.2	0.997	38.0	0.985	41.6	0.994	0.891	1.157	1.269	-10.9	15.7	26.9
Anilofos	230.7	0.999	221.0	1.000	161.5	0.993	180.7	0.988	0.958	0.700	0.783	-4.2	-30.0	-21.7
Atrazine	633.9	0.999	606.0	0.999	739.4	1.000	709.7	0.998	0.956	1.166	1.120	-4.4	16.6	12.0
Azinphos-ethyl	116.5	0.940	84.5	0.973	78.4	0.953	75.7	0.989	0.725	0.673	0.650	-27.5	-32.7	-35.0
Azoxystrobin	725.5	0.999	680.6	0.997	724.9	0.999	746.0	1.000	0.938	0.999	1.028	-6.2	-0.1	2.8
Benalaxyl	259.2	0.999	259.9	0.999	216.7	0.998	223.7	0.991	1.003	0.836	0.863	0.3	-16.4	-13.7
Bendiocarb	206.4	0.978	216.7	0.988	250.7	0.985	138.0	0.952	1.050	1.214	0.669	5.0	21.4	-33.1
Bromacil	49.5	0.993	40.6	0.992	50.4	0.994	52.6	0.999	0.821	1.017	1.062	-17.9	1.7	6.2
Bromuconazole	147.0	1.000	129.5	1.000	107.4	0.995	122.8	0.994	0.881	0.730	0.835	-11.9	-27.0	-16.5
Bupirimate	414.7	1.000	383.0	1.000	353.0	0.997	378.0	0.976	0.924	0.851	0.912	-7.6	-14.9	-8.8
Buprofezin	708.6	0.998	628.2	0.999	369.1	0.952	357.0	1.000	0.887	0.521	0.504	-11.3	-47.9	-49.6
Butocarboxin	74.2	0.977	61.1	0.992	71.7	0.997	41.5	0.995	0.824	0.967	0.559	-17.6	-3.3	-44.1
Butoxycarboxin	9.3	0.998	8.1	0.998	9.7	0.996	9.8	0.988	0.870	1.039	1.053	-13.0	3.9	5.3
Cambendazole	334.3	0.999	279.5	0.999	320.2	1.000	357.7	0.998	0.836	0.958	1.070	-16.4	-4.2	7.0
Carbaryl	22.0	0.999	26.6	1.000	10.0	0.980	8.7	0.998	1.212	0.455	0.395	21.2	-54.5	-60.5
Carbendazim	476.4	0.994	381.8	0.998	487.9	0.992	514.3	0.994	0.801	1.024	1.079	-19.9	2.4	7.9
Carbofuran	393.5	0.981	422.5	0.999	412.5	0.999	182.3	0.989	1.074	1.048	0.463	7.4	4.8	-53.7
Chlorbromuron	21.1	0.993	16.6	0.995	18.3	0.989	20.1	0.996	0.787	0.869	0.952	-21.3	-13.1	-4.8
Chlorfenvinphos	103.1	0.996	93.1	0.998	76.6	0.994	86.1	0.996	0.903	0.743	0.835	-9.7	-25.7	-16.5
Chloridazon	32.4	0.982	27.4	0.989	29.4	0.995	31.1	0.995	0.845	0.907	0.960	-15.5	-9.3	-4.0
Chlorotoluron	248.9	0.990	215.9	0.997	251.5	0.999	143.9	0.982	0.867	1.010	0.578	-13.3	1.0	-42.2
Chloroxuron	241.2	0.998	230.8	0.999	217.5	0.997	228.1	0.996	0.957	0.901	0.945	-4.3	-9.9	-5.5
Chromafenozide	753.6	0.999	696.0	0.999	614.4	0.998	690.6	0.997	0.923	0.815	0.916	-7.7	-18.5	-8.4
Clofentezine	24.3	0.999	20.3	0.994	12.7	0.981	13.0	0.989	0.835	0.522	0.533	-16.5	-47.8	-46.7
Cyproconazole	573.6	1.000	547.3	0.999	656.0	1.000	690.8	0.997	0.954	1.144	1.204	-4.6	14.4	20.4
Cyprodinil	282.0	0.999	260.5	1.000	183.1	0.979	179.7	0.980	0.924	0.649	0.637	-7.6	-35.1	-36.3
Cyromazine	79.2	0.994	30.6	0.997	78.5	0.908	34.9	0.944	0.386	0.990	0.441	-61.4	-1.0	-55.9
Deet	1166.1	0.998	1115.6	0.998	1386.4	0.999	1124.9	0.996	0.957	1.189	0.965	-4.3	18.9	-3.5
Demeton-S-methyl	151.1	0.998	133.2	0.992	137.4	0.998	158.4	0.998	0.882	0.909	1.049	-11.8	-9.1	4.9
Desethylterbutylazine	726.1	1.000	632.4	0.999	694.5	0.999	777.0	0.999	0.871	0.956	1.070	-12.9	-4.4	7.0
Diazinon	2640.6	0.999	2407.3	0.998	2395.0	0.999	2588.1	0.984	0.912	0.907	0.980	-8.8	-9.3	-2.0
Dichlorvos	115.7	0.993	99.4	0.990	108.2	0.997	114.7	0.994	0.860	0.936	0.992	-14.0	-6.4	-0.8
Dicloran	6.5	0.995	5.7	0.999	6.1	0.990	5.9	0.994	0.877	0.944	0.905	-12.3	-5.6	-9.5
Diethofencarb	324.6	0.999	309.3	0.999	301.0	0.999	300.0	0.999	0.953	0.927	0.924	-4.7	-7.3	-7.6

Difenoconazole	806.6	0.999	674.7	1.000	523.3	0.934	687.1	0.988	0.836	0.649	0.852	-16.4	-35.1	-14.8
Difenoconazole	180.5	0.998	169.3	0.995	192.1	0.997	173.6	0.996	0.938	1.064	0.961	-6.2	6.4	-3.9
Diflubenzuron	63.2	1.000	53.2	1.000	44.2	0.998	45.8	0.998	0.842	0.700	0.725	-15.8	-30.0	-27.5
Dimethoate	69.8	0.989	60.4	0.997	72.9	0.999	77.5	0.999	0.866	1.045	1.110	-13.4	4.5	11.0
Dimethomorph	163.8	1.000	142.9	0.998	159.5	0.999	184.6	1.000	0.872	0.974	1.127	-12.8	-2.6	12.7
Dimethylvinphos	233.0	0.998	189.9	0.996	200.0	0.998	210.7	0.999	0.815	0.858	0.904	-18.5	-14.2	-9.6
Diuron	276.0	0.997	254.2	0.996	308.0	0.999	307.6	0.999	0.921	1.116	1.115	-7.9	11.6	11.5
Edifenphos	237.6	0.999	215.8	1.000	164.7	0.999	194.7	0.987	0.908	0.693	0.819	-9.2	-30.7	-18.1
Emamectin benzoate	167.6	0.999	130.5	0.999	85.1	0.990	58.3	0.995	0.779	0.508	0.348	-22.1	-49.2	-65.2
Ethiofencarb	405.0	0.998	355.5	0.998	312.7	0.986	176.4	0.996	0.878	0.772	0.435	-12.2	-22.8	-56.5
Ethion	87.4	0.998	45.8	0.981	18.7	0.917	12.2	0.998	0.524	0.214	0.139	-47.6	-78.6	-86.1
Ethiprole	138.8	1.000	138.5	1.000	142.1	1.000	136.7	1.000	0.997	1.023	0.985	-0.3	2.3	-1.5
Ethoxyquin	3.0	0.981	2.9	0.938	2.3	0.961	3.5	0.977	0.967	0.765	1.170	-3.3	-23.5	17.0
Fenamiphos	384.7	1.000	340.3	0.999	325.5	1.000	385.1	0.999	0.885	0.846	1.001	-11.5	-15.4	0.1
Fenarimol	109.6	1.000	94.1	1.000	103.8	0.997	121.1	0.994	0.859	0.947	1.105	-14.1	-5.3	10.5
Fenazaquin	389.7	0.999	229.7	0.981	137.7	0.964	82.8	0.999	0.589	0.353	0.212	-41.1	-64.7	-78.8
Fenbendazole	1101.7	0.999	907.5	0.999	746.4	0.992	914.7	0.989	0.824	0.677	0.830	-17.6	-32.3	-17.0
Fenhexamid	92.1	0.999	81.1	0.999	72.1	0.994	78.8	0.996	0.881	0.783	0.856	-11.9	-21.7	-14.4
Fenobucarb	444.9	0.996	417.5	0.996	470.0	0.998	464.9	1.000	0.938	1.056	1.045	-6.2	5.6	4.5
Fenoxycarb	176.6	0.998	155.5	0.999	123.3	0.992	146.7	0.989	0.881	0.698	0.830	-11.9	-30.2	-17.0
Fenuron	292.5	0.997	236.4	0.998	305.3	0.999	305.2	0.999	0.808	1.044	1.043	-19.2	4.4	4.3
Fipronil	15.1	0.987	4.2	0.987	2.2	0.928	9.5	0.997	0.281	0.147	0.631	-71.9	-85.3	-36.9
Flazasulfuron	306.9	1.000	223.0	0.992	244.2	0.993	279.2	0.999	0.727	0.796	0.910	-27.3	-20.4	-9.0
Fluacrypyrim	1067.6	0.997	972.8	0.999	667.2	0.990	739.5	0.986	0.911	0.625	0.693	-8.9	-37.5	-30.7
Fluazifop	243.6	1.000	230.8	0.999	269.2	0.999	282.9	1.000	0.948	1.105	1.161	-5.2	10.5	16.1
Flufenoxuron	156.3	0.979	43.5	0.713	17.8	0.750	10.6	0.859	0.278	0.114	0.068	-72.2	-88.6	-93.2
Fluometuron	352.1	0.997	344.6	0.996	402.5	0.999	384.7	0.999	0.979	1.143	1.093	-2.1	14.3	9.3
Fluquinconazole	93.3	1.000	85.6	1.000	91.2	0.999	97.2	0.989	0.917	0.978	1.042	-8.3	-2.2	4.2
Fluroxypyr	14.3	0.999	12.2	0.994	15.2	0.998	14.4	0.990	0.851	1.064	1.006	-14.9	6.4	0.6
Hexaflumuron	85.8	0.991	46.4	0.960	21.8	0.943	16.8	0.998	0.541	0.254	0.196	-45.9	-74.6	-80.4
Hexythiazox	99.3	0.999	60.2	0.979	30.6	0.964	22.5	0.998	0.607	0.308	0.226	-39.3	-69.2	-77.4
Imazalil	123.7	0.997	100.0	0.998	99.4	0.995	114.5	0.988	0.809	0.804	0.926	-19.1	-19.6	-7.4
Imidacloprid	36.7	0.994	33.5	0.998	41.3	0.995	42.9	0.999	0.913	1.125	1.170	-8.7	12.5	17.0
Indoxacarb	53.2	0.999	43.8	0.998	19.7	0.979	20.7	0.997	0.822	0.371	0.390	-17.8	-62.9	-61.0
Iprodione	37.3	0.988	37.0	0.998	34.6	0.981	35.8	0.990	0.993	0.928	0.960	-0.7	-7.2	-4.0
Isocarbofos	1.8	0.915	1.2	0.898	1.7	0.934	2.2	0.978	0.642	0.927	1.214	-35.8	-7.3	21.4
Isofenfos methyl	266.1	0.999	241.6	0.999	177.5	0.995	205.3	0.991	0.908	0.667	0.771	-9.2	-33.3	-22.9
Isoprocab	338.3	0.996	332.9	0.998	346.6	0.998	308.2	0.999	0.984	1.025	0.911	-1.6	2.5	-8.9
Isoproturon	384.4	0.997	371.3	0.996	432.5	0.998	301.5	0.991	0.966	1.125	0.784	-3.4	12.5	-21.6
Kresoxim-methyl	16.3	0.932	13.9	0.961	18.4	0.948	17.2	0.988	0.855	1.131	1.054	-14.5	13.1	5.4
Lenacil	254.4	0.999	230.2	0.998	255.0	1.000	267.6	0.998	0.905	1.003	1.052	-9.5	0.3	5.2
Linuron	54.5	0.996	44.8	0.997	53.3	0.998	47.9	0.998	0.822	0.978	0.879	-17.8	-2.2	-12.1
Lufenuron	74.6	0.983	25.6	0.771	10.5	0.830	7.1	0.909	0.344	0.141	0.095	-65.6	-85.9	-90.5
Malathion	227.7	0.999	221.5	1.000	210.0	0.999	209.5	0.995	0.973	0.922	0.920	-2.7	-7.8	-8.0
Mebendazole	657.9	1.000	566.3	0.999	663.0	0.997	713.0	0.997	0.861	1.008	1.084	-13.9	0.8	8.4
Metalaxyl	256.1	0.998	256.0	0.999	254.2	0.997	248.0	0.999	1.000	0.992	0.968	0.0	-0.8	-3.2
Metamitron	120.4	0.998	103.8	0.999	128.3	1.000	128.0	0.999	0.862	1.066	1.063	-13.8	6.6	6.3
Methamidophos	49.3	0.983	30.7	0.955	49.5	0.989	46.2	0.999	0.622	1.003	0.936	-37.8	0.3	-6.4
Methidathion	83.5	0.998	74.0	0.988	64.6	0.999	60.5	0.999	0.885	0.774	0.724	-11.5	-22.6	-27.6

Methiocarb	214.5	0.997	205.1	0.999	207.1	0.998	207.7	0.998	0.956	0.965	0.968	-4.4	-3.5	-3.2
Methiocarb sulfoxide	106.5	0.965	89.5	0.954	97.4	0.957	74.6	0.952	0.841	0.914	0.701	-15.9	-8.6	-29.9
Methomyl	22.4	0.913	19.2	0.964	21.0	0.922	22.1	0.984	0.859	0.939	0.986	-14.1	-6.1	-1.4
Methoxyfenozide	788.5	0.999	770.4	0.999	737.8	0.999	764.1	0.998	0.977	0.936	0.969	-2.3	-6.4	-3.1
Metobromuron	4.3	0.993	3.2	0.979	3.4	0.997	4.3	0.978	0.732	0.793	0.985	-26.8	-20.7	-1.5
Metolachlor	610.1	0.999	612.2	0.999	559.3	1.000	565.5	0.997	1.003	0.917	0.927	0.3	-8.3	-7.3
Metolcarb	166.9	0.997	131.4	0.984	179.8	0.999	196.1	0.999	0.787	1.077	1.175	-21.3	7.7	17.5
Miconazole	177.2	0.995	76.0	0.916	48.8	0.915	53.9	0.998	0.429	0.275	0.304	-57.1	-72.5	-69.6
Monocrotophos	64.6	0.997	53.5	0.997	71.3	0.995	80.5	0.997	0.829	1.104	1.245	-17.1	10.4	24.5
Monolinuron	54.5	0.996	43.6	0.992	75.2	0.964	36.7	0.975	0.800	1.381	0.674	-20.0	38.1	-32.6
Monuron	134.9	0.994	131.1	0.997	157.7	0.999	147.1	0.993	0.972	1.169	1.090	-2.8	16.9	9.0
Myclobutanil	465.5	1.000	433.7	1.000	537.4	1.000	547.1	0.996	0.932	1.154	1.175	-6.8	15.4	17.5
Neburon	109.7	0.997	102.5	0.999	90.2	0.995	101.0	0.991	0.935	0.822	0.921	-6.5	-17.8	-7.9
Nitempyram	42.1	0.998	37.0	0.997	46.6	0.995	50.4	0.995	0.878	1.108	1.196	-12.2	10.8	19.6
Omethoate	49.1	0.992	29.1	0.996	51.6	0.984	53.3	0.997	0.591	1.051	1.084	-40.9	5.1	8.4
Oxadixyl	105.2	0.999	102.2	0.999	123.3	1.000	127.9	0.999	0.971	1.172	1.215	-2.9	17.2	21.5
Oxamyl	93.8	0.986	91.2	0.981	93.9	0.956	109.7	0.962	0.973	1.002	1.170	-2.7	0.2	17.0
Oxfendazole	134.5	0.999	123.2	0.999	160.1	1.000	162.1	0.999	0.916	1.190	1.205	-8.4	19.0	20.5
Parathion-ethyl	85.4	0.996	72.7	1.000	60.7	0.993	71.6	0.988	0.852	0.711	0.839	-14.8	-28.9	-16.1
Penconazole	526.8	1.000	502.1	0.999	516.3	0.999	570.7	0.990	0.953	0.980	1.083	-4.7	-2.0	8.3
Pirimicarb	464.4	0.999	376.1	0.999	457.4	0.998	533.4	0.999	0.810	0.985	1.149	-19.0	-1.5	14.9
Pirimiphos-methyl	986.7	0.998	841.1	0.999	658.6	0.990	764.8	0.991	0.852	0.667	0.775	-14.8	-33.3	-22.5
Prochloraz	236.6	0.999	206.9	1.000	169.3	0.993	208.8	0.984	0.874	0.716	0.883	-12.6	-28.4	-11.7
Procymidone	14.4	0.997	12.7	0.997	12.2	0.997	13.5	0.998	0.886	0.846	0.942	-11.4	-15.4	-5.8
Promecarb	368.4	0.996	312.4	0.993	342.2	0.996	352.8	0.999	0.848	0.929	0.958	-15.2	-7.1	-4.2
Prometryn	320.9	1.000	308.0	0.999	312.1	0.999	329.1	0.989	0.960	0.973	1.026	-4.0	-2.7	2.6
Propamocarb	264.3	0.995	176.8	0.979	288.9	0.993	275.2	0.947	0.669	1.093	1.041	-33.1	9.3	4.1
Propargite	16.0	0.989	7.0	0.947	3.6	0.773	1.6	0.981	0.440	0.226	0.099	-56.0	-77.4	-90.1
Propazine	485.3	1.000	441.4	1.000	507.0	1.000	486.8	0.988	0.909	1.045	1.003	-9.1	4.5	0.3
Pyridaben	528.4	0.990	230.9	0.857	90.8	0.773	43.9	0.962	0.437	0.172	0.083	-56.3	-82.8	-91.7
Pyridaphenthion	373.9	1.000	345.2	0.999	330.5	1.000	353.8	0.997	0.923	0.884	0.946	-7.7	-11.6	-5.4
Pyrimethanil	149.8	0.998	122.7	0.998	140.3	0.999	144.9	0.986	0.819	0.937	0.967	-18.1	-6.3	-3.3
Pyriproxyfen	2094.4	0.999	1339.6	0.974	819.1	0.952	522.4	0.998	0.640	0.391	0.249	-36.0	-60.9	-75.1
Quinalphos	201.2	0.999	181.4	1.000	163.4	0.995	184.9	0.985	0.901	0.812	0.919	-9.9	-18.8	-8.1
Quinoxifen	534.6	1.000	352.2	0.986	224.5	0.964	168.7	0.996	0.659	0.420	0.316	-34.1	-58.0	-68.4
Simazine	210.0	1.000	198.2	0.999	236.7	1.000	224.7	0.999	0.944	1.127	1.070	-5.6	12.7	7.0
Spinosyn A	657.2	0.998	561.7	0.999	507.3	0.996	527.8	0.994	0.855	0.772	0.803	-14.5	-22.8	-19.7
Spinosyn D	117.8	0.997	86.5	0.994	61.8	0.978	80.0	0.996	0.734	0.525	0.679	-26.6	-47.5	-32.1
Spiroxamine	1078.3	1.000	1021.5	1.000	1085.3	0.998	1215.2	0.998	0.947	1.006	1.127	-5.3	0.6	12.7
Tebuconazole	636.4	1.000	603.7	0.999	679.9	0.999	709.1	0.992	0.949	1.068	1.114	-5.1	6.8	11.4
Tebufenozide	36.1	0.998	36.7	0.998	29.0	0.993	30.7	0.994	1.017	0.805	0.850	1.7	-19.5	-15.0
Tebufenpyrad	122.4	1.000	92.7	1.000	59.6	0.986	62.0	0.993	0.758	0.487	0.506	-24.2	-51.3	-49.4
Teftubenzuron	37.2	0.996	25.2	0.987	13.0	0.964	12.8	0.999	0.676	0.350	0.344	-32.4	-65.0	-65.6
Terbuthylazine	1652.9	0.999	1559.6	0.999	1704.8	1.000	1660.0	0.989	0.944	1.031	1.004	-5.6	3.1	0.4
Terbutrin	1193.0	1.000	1128.6	0.999	1093.8	0.998	1138.1	0.985	0.946	0.917	0.954	-5.4	-8.3	-4.6
Thiabendazole	4.2	0.977	3.6	0.986	4.9	0.996	4.7	0.990	0.848	1.169	1.118	-15.2	16.9	11.8
Thiacloprid	167.0	0.994	146.5	0.994	140.6	0.989	157.3	0.997	0.877	0.842	0.942	-12.3	-15.8	-5.8
Thiametoxam	32.4	0.996	29.8	0.987	31.0	0.995	36.3	0.989	0.919	0.957	1.121	-8.1	-4.3	12.1
Thiocyclam	224.8	0.995	174.3	0.990	264.5	0.999	330.0	1.000	0.775	1.177	1.468	-22.5	17.7	46.8

Thiophanate-ethyl	318.2	0.999	293.3	0.999	205.5	0.997	100.6	0.960	0.922	0.646	0.316	-7.8	-35.4	-68.4
Tolfenpyrad	179.2	0.999	118.6	0.992	68.7	0.961	57.6	0.999	0.662	0.383	0.321	-33.8	-61.7	-67.9
TPP	249.2	0.998	190.7	0.995	152.0	0.994	169.0	0.998	0.765	0.610	0.678	-23.5	-39.0	-32.2
Triadimefon	206.3	1.000	192.0	0.998	229.5	1.000	238.0	0.996	0.931	1.113	1.154	-6.9	11.3	15.4
Triadimenol	364.9	1.000	352.2	0.998	438.4	1.000	432.5	0.997	0.965	1.202	1.185	-3.5	20.2	18.5
Triazophos	382.4	1.000	401.8	1.000	364.8	0.999	370.8	0.990	1.051	0.954	0.970	5.1	-4.6	-3.0
Triclocarban	33.7	0.998	16.3	0.935	9.6	0.916	6.0	0.991	0.484	0.284	0.177	-51.6	-71.6	-82.3
Trifloxystrobin	437.1	0.999	391.0	0.996	211.0	0.985	215.8	0.991	0.895	0.483	0.494	-10.5	-51.7	-50.6
Triflumizol	529.9	0.999	404.1	0.999	308.6	0.993	398.7	0.989	0.763	0.582	0.752	-23.7	-41.8	-24.8
Triflumuron	122.1	0.996	99.0	0.997	61.4	0.977	69.9	0.997	0.810	0.502	0.572	-19.0	-49.8	-42.8
XMC	89.5	0.937	77.2	0.995	95.3	0.962	61.0	0.793	0.863	1.064	0.682	-13.7	6.4	-31.8

Table 3. Results of the uncertainty study.

Recovery	Tomato ^a	Pear ^a	Orange ^a	10 ppb ^b	100 ppb ^b	Overall ^c
Mean	93.8	87.5	89.4	88.2	92.2	90.2
Number of data	1500	1500	1500	2250	2250	4500
SD	14.2	13.1	13.9	15.7	11.8	14.0
RSD	0.1512	0.1499	0.1559	0.1780	0.1278	0.1551

$$U_{exp} = k \times RSD_{overall} = 2 \times 0.1551 = 0.300.$$

^a Data of 10 and 100 ng g⁻¹ fortification level.

^b Data of tomato, pear and orange together.

^c Data of 10 and 100 ng g⁻¹ fortification level in tomato pear and orange together.